

Genomic characterization of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in Sludge Produced from Wastewater Treatment Plants in Gaza Strip: Environmental Health Impact

Rania Ghoneim¹, Adnan Al-Hindi^{2,*}, Nahed Al Laham³

¹ The joint Ph.D. program in water technology, Institute-Water & Environment, Al-Azhar University, Gaza Strip, Palestine.

² Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, Faculty of Health Sciences - Islamic University of Gaza, P.O. Box 108, Gaza, Palestine.

³ Department of Laboratory Medicine, Faculty of Applied Medical Sciences, Al Azhar University-Gaza, Gaza Strip, Palestine.

***. Corresponding author:** Adnan Al-Hindi, Medical Laboratory Sciences Department, Faculty of Health Sciences - Islamic University of Gaza, P.O. Box 108, Gaza, Palestine. Phone: +4407788843096. Email: Adnan.Alhindi@glasgow.ac.uk.

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Abstract

Background: Massive amounts of sludge created by wastewater treatment in the Gaza Strip that are not treated may pose a health risk due to the protozoa and other diseases prevalent in the sludge. The current work sought to identify the genetic characteristics of *Cryptosporidium* spp. and other protozoa found in sludge from wastewater treatment plants in the Gaza Strip.

Materials and methods: Between December 2021 and August 2022, 72 sludge samples were collected from the Gaza Strip's three municipal wastewater treatment plants, each of which uses a different biological treatment procedure. Following transfer to the laboratory, materials were coded and microscopically examined using the modified Ziehl-Neelsen (MZN) method. The results were then validated using the Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA), PCR, and sequence analysis for *Cryptosporidium* spp.

Results: The MZN stain identified 16/72 (22.2%), while the ELISA identified 9/72 (12.5%) of the *Cryptosporidium* spp. samples. Using the PCR technique, only 3/72 (4.2%) of the samples tested positive for *Cryptosporidium* spp. The three positive *Cryptosporidium* samples were identified as *Cryptosporidium parvum* by sequencing. The nucleotide sequences of *Cryptosporidium* spp. were found to be highly similar using Sanger dideoxy sequencing (more than 96% similarity). The sequences discovered in this work have been submitted to GenBank with the accession numbers OQ104414, OQ104415, and OQ104416.

Conclusion: The sludge from sewage plants was found to be polluted and confirmed as *Cryptosporidium parvum* using several techniques.

Keywords: Wastewater treatment plants, sludge, Protozoa, *Cryptosporidium* spp., PCR, Sequencing, Gaza, Palestine

Introduction

Sludge is produced in vast quantities as a byproduct of wastewater treatment. The principal treatment procedures used include aerobic and anaerobic

digestion, thickening, and classic sludge drying beds (1). The Gaza Strip's freshwater scarcity is the result of increased human use, decreased yearly precipitation, and overcrowding. For these reasons, the government promotes the recycling of treated

wastewater. Public health concerns have been expressed concerning the risk of parasite infection from water source contamination caused by the reuse of wastewater or sludge in agriculture (2). The dewatered sludge is then moved to the Municipality of the Gaza Strip-controlled landfill in Johr-AL Dik. However, the pathogens present in the sludge could pose a health risk, so the accumulation of sludge from the wastewater treatment process and its disposal without microorganism treatment could be problematic (3). The dewatered sludge is then moved to the Municipality of the Gaza Strip-controlled landfill in Johr-AL Dik. However, the pathogens present in the sludge could pose a health risk, so the accumulation of sludge from the wastewater treatment process and its disposal without microorganism treatment could be problematic (3). Like in other developing nations, parasitic illnesses are seen as a neglected health problem in Palestine, while being one of the leading causes of morbidity in Palestinian society. According to the Palestinian Ministry of Health (MoH), thousands of Palestinians have become ill as a result of parasite exposure (4). Parasites that cause diarrhea include nematodes and intestinal protozoa. They are common, but they are more common in underdeveloped nations where contaminated water is the cause of 485,000 deaths annually, of which 297,000 are children under the age of five (5).

A new environmental problem that has emerged recently as a result of the expansion of wastewater treatment plants is the buildup of sludge from the wastewater treatment process. Although experts are working to find a solution, using sewage sludge as a natural fertilizer on farms is currently the most practical option to lower these volumes (6). Municipal wastewater has high levels of microbiological and chemical pollution. These species, which include parasitic and bacterial contaminations, may enter the purifying process and change the treatment plant into a unique ecosystem. The bacteria were not completely removed following the treatment process, and wastewater discharge could allow them to find their way into natural environments. Municipal wastewater treatment plants are usually designed to remove organic contaminants; hence, they rarely remove heavy metals, parasite eggs, or dangerous microorganisms. During wastewater treatment, pathogens, organic substances, and other contaminants should be eliminated (7).

The results of the most recent studies on *cryptosporidium* spp. in children showed that, when samples were tested using the ELISA and acid-fast staining techniques, 14.9% and 16.3% of the samples tested positive (8). According to another study, 14.9% of stool samples from Gaza, Palestine had

cryptosporidiosis (4). The goal of the current work was to characterize *Cryptosporidium* spp. genomically in sludge that was generated from Gaza Strip wastewater treatment plants.

Material and Methods

Study sites and samples

The three municipal wastewater treatment plants implicated in this study are located in the Gaza Strip and use various biological treatment procedures.

Seventy-two (72) dewatering sludge samples were collected from three wastewater treatment plants in Gaza-Strip: the Khan Younis Waste Water Treatment Plant (KYWWTP), the central sewage treatment plant east of Al-Bureij (CSTP), and the Northern Gaza Wastewater Treatment Plant. All of the factories employ different processes to treat wastewater and sludge. Each sludge sample weighs 100 grams and is collected in a sterile cup.

These samples were gathered over a period of eight months, from December to July 2022. Every month, three dewatering sludge samples were taken from each WWTP at 10-day intervals. The samples were obtained at the same time, at 10:00 a.m. Samples were delivered immediately to the Islamic University of Gaza laboratory (PCR and sequencing samples were sent to Egypt and evaluated at the Animal Health Research Institute in Dokii, Egypt).

Modified Ziehl Neelsen method (acid-fast stain): All sludge samples were coded and transported to the laboratory, where a sludge smear was produced, fixed with methanol, dried, stained using the modified Ziehl Neelsen procedure, and viewed under a 100X objective (9).

Detection of Cryptosporidium spp. Antigens by ELISA: The coproantigen of *Cryptosporidium* spp. was detected using a commercial ELISA kit for stool samples (MONOSCREEN *Cryptosporidium*, Bio-x diagnostic S.A, Belgique) according to the manufacturer's recommendations. The MONOSCREEN *Cryptosporidium* test uses particular antibodies in a sandwich-type approach. *Cryptosporidium*-specific antibodies against *Cryptosporidium* spp. antigens are added to the microwell plate's surface. The ELISA kit includes: Microwell plate wells coated with *Cryptosporidium*-specific antibodies, washing solution, colored dilution buffer, conjugate control antigen, and stopping solution.

Pipette a suspension of the test sludge sample and the controls into the microwell plate's wells. Next, antibodies conjugated with peroxidase against *Cryptosporidium* spp. antigens are added to the plate, which is then incubated for one hour at room temperature (20 - 25°C). The negative and positive controls from the kits were used. The optical density (OD) of each sample was measured at 450 nm with a microplate reader. Samples were declared positive if their extinction exceeded the calculated cut-off by more than 10%, as given in the manufacturer's formula. If the test is affirmative, the connected enzyme turns the previously colorless solution in the wells of the microwell plate blue. When you add the stop reagent, the color changes from blue to yellow. The extinction rate is proportional to the amount of *Cryptosporidium* antigen present in the sample.

DNA extraction and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) were performed on sludge samples that tested positive by MZN for *Cryptosporidium* infection and sensitivity. In addition, negative samples were evaluated for specificity and *Cryptosporidium* infection detection using MZN (pooling). The QIAamp DNA Mini Kit purifies nucleic acids from a variety of sources using a silica membrane. To detect *Cryptosporidium* spp., a primary PCR was performed with the Cry9 and Cry15 genes as targets. The forward primer was 5'-GGACTGAAATACAGGCATTATCTTG -3', while the reverse primer was 5'-GTAGATAATGGAAGAGATTGTG -3'. PCR amplification yielded approximately 553 bp depending on the *Cryptosporidium* species (10).

The amplified products were observed using 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis and ethidium bromide staining. Each PCR experiment included control samples (negative control) and positive control (*Cryptosporidium* spp. genomic DNA). A commercial company (BMR Genomics, Padua, Italy) performed bidirectional sequencing on the PCR results.

A purified PCR product was sequenced in the forward and/or reverse directions using an applied Biosystems 3130 automated DNA sequencer (ABI, 3130, USA). Initially, a ready reaction Bigdye Terminator V3.1 cycle sequencing kit (11) was used to demonstrate sequence identity with GenBank accessions.

Results

The microscopic inspection of 72 WWTP sludge samples stained with MZN (Figure 1), which exhibits the pink color of the identified *Cryptosporidium* oocyst, revealed that 16 (22.2%) samples tested positive for *Cryptosporidium* spp. Using the PCR

technique, only 3/16 (4.2%) were positive for *Cryptosporidium* spp. (Figure 2). The three *Cryptosporidium*-positive samples were identified as *Cryptosporidium parvum* by sequencing. All *Cryptosporidium* spp. nucleotide sequences evaluated by Sanger dideoxy sequencing exhibited high similarity (above 96%). The nucleotide sequences found in our investigation were placed in the GenBank database under the accession codes OQ104414, OQ104415, and OQ104416 (Figure 3).

Discussion

The current study provides some preliminary data on the prevalence of the waterborne pathogen *Cryptosporidium* spp. in Gaza Strip sludge. The current study verified sludge contamination by *Cryptosporidium* spp. in Gaza's sewage plants. Direct sequencing of the positive PCR results verifies the most prevalent species exhibited in sludge samples. *Cryptosporidium parvum* was found in WWTP sludge, and *Cryptosporidium* spp. were identified in MEGA6 using maximum likelihood, neighbor-joining, and sequence comparisons, indicating that this species may have originated only from people and animals. *Cryptosporidium parvum* is responsible for 90% of *Cryptosporidium* infections, hence its presence in urban wastewater is not unusual. The concentration of *C. parvum* in the sludge was substantially higher than in the wastewater, which could be attributed to trickling filters' inefficiency in eliminating it.

The protozoan parasite *Cryptosporidium* has been described as a significant waterborne disease pathogen, and it is associated with severe gastrointestinal disorders in the Gaza Strip. Cryptosporidiosis is linked to their presence in kitchen filters (12). *Cryptosporidium* is the second leading cause of moderate to severe diarrhea and mortality in children under the age of five in underdeveloped nations (13).

Our investigation found that all *Cryptosporidium parvum* nucleotide sequences were 100% identical. Figure 4 depicts the sequencing of the COWP gene, which demonstrated a 100% maximal identity (among themselves). In our investigation, the sequenced strains of *Cryptosporidium parvum* were clustered in the gene bank under accession numbers OQ104414, OQ104415, and OQ104416.

Figure 1. The stained *Cryptosporidium* oocyst with MZN.

Figure 2. The PCR result of *Cryptosporidium* spp. using ethidium bromide staining and detected with gel electrophoresis (1.5 agarose\100ml TAE). Lane **L**: 100 bp DNA ladder, lane **P** indicates the positive control (553bp), lane **N** indicates the negative control. Lanes 5, 9, and 12 indicate the presence of *Cryptosporidium* spp. (553 bp).

Figure 3. Molecular Phylogenetic Analysis of *Cryptosporidium* spp.

		Percent Identity																											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25			
Divergence	1	100.0	98.7	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	1	BX538351 <i>C. parvum</i>	
	2	0.0	100.0	98.7	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	2	AB089292 <i>C. parvum</i>	
	3	0.7	0.7	100.0	98.7	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.2	96.5	97.4	90.0	85.6	82.8	85.2	84.1	77.3	91.5	95.6	96.5	94.8	88.0	82.6	3	Z22537 <i>C. parvum</i>
	4	0.0	0.0	0.7	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	4	DQ388390 <i>C. parvum</i>	
	5	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	5	KY706489 <i>C. parvum</i>	
	6	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	6	MK033059 <i>C. parvum</i> W6	
	7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	99.8	99.8	99.8	98.5	97.8	98.7	91.1	86.7	83.7	85.8	85.4	78.0	92.6	96.9	97.8	95.9	89.3	83.7	7	AB514064 <i>C. parvum</i> Sakha210	
	8	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	100.0	100.0	98.3	97.6	98.5	90.8	86.5	83.4	85.6	85.2	77.8	92.8	96.7	97.6	95.6	89.1	83.9	8	OQ104414 <i>C. parvum</i> CryM8		
	9	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	100.0	98.3	97.6	98.5	90.8	86.5	83.4	85.6	85.2	77.8	92.8	96.7	97.6	95.6	89.1	83.9	9	OQ104415 <i>C. parvum</i> CryKh6		
	10	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	98.3	97.6	98.5	90.8	86.5	83.4	85.6	85.2	77.8	92.8	96.7	97.6	95.6	89.1	83.9	10	OQ104416 <i>C. parvum</i> CryN9		
	11	1.5	1.5	2.2	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.8	1.8	1.8	97.6	98.0	90.4	86.5	82.8	85.6	85.2	77.8	92.8	96.7	97.6	96.1	89.1	83.4	11	MK033061 <i>C. hominis</i> W8		
	12	2.2	2.2	2.9	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	97.4	91.5	86.7	83.2	86.3	86.3	78.6	93.5	97.8	98.3	96.3	89.3	84.1	12	AF266271 <i>C. wrairi</i>
	13	1.3	1.3	2.0	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.5	2.0	2.7	97.4	90.6	86.7	83.2	85.4	85.4	77.6	93.2	96.5	97.4	95.9	88.9	83.7	13	MH912965 <i>C. tyzzeri</i> 23228	
	14	9.6	9.6	10.2	9.6	9.6	9.6	9.6	9.8	9.8	9.8	10.4	9.1	10.1	10.1	86.1	83.2	86.5	85.6	78.2	90.6	90.6	91.1	92.2	87.8	81.5	14	XM_029019345 <i>C. ubiquitum</i> EB	
	15	14.8	14.8	15.5	14.8	14.8	14.8	14.8	15.1	15.1	15.1	15.1	14.8	14.8	15.7	82.1	94.3	88.2	76.7	85.8	86.3	87.6	86.7	88.0	84.5	15	MG266045 <i>C. ditrichi</i> 12667		
	16	18.5	18.5	18.9	18.5	18.5	18.5	18.5	18.8	18.8	18.8	19.6	19.1	19.1	19.0	20.5	81.3	80.2	79.7	82.6	83.7	83.0	83.0	81.5	82.4	16	DQ060432 <i>C. baileyi</i> Tcb		
	17	16.0	16.0	16.1	16.0	16.0	16.0	16.0	16.2	16.2	16.2	16.2	15.4	16.6	15.2	6.0	21.7	87.6	77.8	86.7	85.8	86.7	86.7	86.9	87.4	83.2	17	MG266046 <i>C. apodemii</i> 30405	
	18	16.4	16.4	17.4	16.4	16.4	16.4	16.4	16.7	16.7	16.7	16.7	15.3	16.4	16.2	13.0	23.2	13.8	75.8	85.6	85.8	85.8	86.3	87.1	81.9	18	LC503970 <i>C. canis</i> CDS-449		
	19	26.3	26.3	26.5	26.3	26.3	26.3	26.6	26.6	26.6	26.6	26.6	25.3	26.9	25.9	28.2	24.0	26.6	29.4	77.1	78.4	78.4	78.2	76.9	77.6	19	KJ917580 <i>C. andersoni</i> Y1		
	20	7.9	7.9	8.5	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.6	7.6	7.6	7.6	6.9	7.1	10.1	16.0	20.0	14.9	16.2	27.6	93.9	93.7	94.3	88.5	83.9	20	JX984441 <i>C. viatorum</i> Swec066		
	21	3.1	3.1	3.8	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.4	3.4	3.4	3.4	2.2	3.6	10.1	15.3	18.5	16.0	15.9	25.6	6.4	97.8	95.4	88.9	83.4	21	AB471654 <i>C. meleagridis</i>		
	22	2.2	2.2	2.9	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4	1.8	2.7	9.6	13.7	19.4	14.8	15.9	25.6	6.7	2.2	96.7	89.3	83.9	22	MZ772045 <i>C. sciurinum</i> 45901		
	23	4.3	4.3	4.8	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.0	3.8	4.3	8.3	14.9	19.4	14.6	15.3	26.0	5.9	4.7	3.4	88.5	83.2	23	KY953225 <i>C. fayeri</i> JJ106		
	24	11.6	11.6	12.5	11.6	11.6	11.6	11.6	11.9	11.9	11.9	11.9	11.1	12.2	13.7	13.2	21.4	14.1	14.3	27.9	12.8	12.2	11.7	12.7	83.0	24	MH145318 <i>C. alticolis</i> 23111		
	25	18.7	18.7	19.4	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.7	18.4	18.4	18.4	19.0	18.2	18.7	21.7	17.5	20.3	19.2	21.2	26.9	18.4	19.0	18.4	19.3	19.5	25	AF266263 <i>C. felis</i>		

Figure 4. Nucleotide identities of the of the 18S rRNA gene for WWTPs of Gaza Strip *Cryptosporidium* spp. isolates with selected references.

It was also discovered that 99.8% nucleotide sequence identity with representative strains BX538351.1, which reported the physical mapping of the Iowa isolate's genome, sequencing and analysis of chromosome 6, and approximately 0.9 Mbp of sequence sampled from the remainder of the genome in Ebersberg (Germany). On the other hand, the three *Cryptosporidium parvum* strains obtained in our investigation had a 99.8% similarity to those described and isolated from humans in Japan in 2005 (AB089292.1).

The zoonotic potential of *Cryptosporidium parvum* (DQ388390.1) was isolated in the Netherlands from the feces of infected people and animals, with a 99.8% similarity to our strains. Tedde evaluated the occurrence and seasonality of zoonotic protozoans in mussels farmed or sold at retail outlets in Italy (KY706489), and their nucleotide sequences were 99.8% identical to our strains. Furthermore, our investigation found 99.5% similarity to other genetically examined *Cryptosporidium parvum* HNJ-1 strains, including the Japanese reference strain recovered from humans in Japan (Z22537.1).

Our findings are consistent with certain research from China (14). Another study in Gaza found that 1.9% of diverse sources of drinking water were infected with *Cryptosporidium* oocysts (15). Several studies around the world have found *Cryptosporidium* spp. in wastewater, including Brazil and Peru (16), China (17), and Europe (18). Several Egyptian investigations revealed *Cryptosporidium* detection rates of 29.7% and 25.5% by nested PCR (19), respectively, and 45% in another study by El-Hady and colleagues (20). Another study in Egypt found that PCR findings detected *Cryptosporidium* spp. in one of the eight tested dry sludge samples (12.5%) (21). Sheather's sucrose flotation technique did not discover *Cryptosporidium* oocysts (4-6 μm) or other sub-species in the dried sludge samples. It was discovered that the average cysts of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in sludge after stabilization (aerobic digestion) were higher than in raw sludge (22). In another study, the average number of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts identified in WWTP influents from Brazil ranged from 24.25 to 332/L, with 33.3% of all samples (n = 54) being negative. WWTP had the highest count of *Cryptosporidium* oocysts in influents, at 580/L (23). Cysts were found in 100% of the studied wastewater samples, however oocysts were found in only 39.0% (24).

Several surrounding nation reports revealed that prevalence rates differed from ours. Other reports produced results comparable to ours. Egypt had 33.3% of *Cryptosporidium* in its sewage and river water (25). Martins and colleagues (16) conducted a similar study in Brazil and discovered that 8% of

samples tested positive for *Cryptosporidium* in both raw and treated sewage. Treatment efficacy in Poland's wastewater treatment plants was 61.5%, which differed from prior research (26). *Cryptosporidium* spp. was discovered in 100% of Malaysian drinking water (27), 96% in Belgian raw water samples (28), and 86.5% in Israeli tertiary effluent (29). About 36.4% in a Lima, Peru wastewater sample (29), and 31.1% in German wastewater (30). On the other hand, the prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* oocyst concentrations was lower in other countries: 0.09% in surface water in Spain (31) and 12.2% in China (32).

This study's ELISA approach detected *Cryptosporidium* spp. in 12.5% (9/72) of sludge samples taken from KYWWTP, CSTPE, and ENGEST. ELISA is the process of immobilizing an antibody against *Cryptosporidium parvum* (or any other particular parasite) on a plate and then adding the sample (antigen). Absorbance spectroscopy necessitates secondary antibodies, and enzymes are often detected in feces samples from humans and animals via ELISA. There is no need to concentrate oocysts from feces prior to processing. Thus, ELISA can quickly examine many feces samples. ELISA is ten times more sensitive than acid-fast staining, detecting 103-104 oocysts/ml (33). Because of the use of various commercial kits, population samples (human/animal), and evaluation references, ELISA results have varied significantly in sensitivity (59-100%) and specificity (93-100%). ELISA processing takes 1-3 hours and can produce false positives. Due to the complex components and low oocyst counts, ELISA cannot detect *Cryptosporidium parvum* or other targeted parasites in water samples. Thus, ELISA tests primarily feces (35).

The investigation was conducted in a tough environment on the Gaza Strip due to power outages and inadequate machine repair in sewage plants. Another problem was the limited period of time required to collect data and samples. We used molecular techniques throughout the investigation to ensure the accuracy of sample diagnosis and adherence to the protocols used in wastewater and sludge diagnosis and processing.

Conclusion

The present investigation established the molecular presence of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in sludge samples using PCR and sequencing. To preserve human and animal health, we urge that Palestinian authorities in the Gaza Strip create measures, protocols, and recommendations for sludge storage, use disposal, transportation, and disinfection.

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References

1. Fernando-Foncillas, C., Estevez, M.M., Uellendahl, H., Varrone, C. Co-management of sewage sludge and other organic wastes: a Scandinavian case study. *Energies* 2021;14(12):3411.
2. Abd-Elaty, I., Abd-Elhamid, H.F., Qahman, K. Coastal Aquifer Protection from Saltwater Intrusion Using Abstraction of Brackish Water and Recharge of Treated Wastewater: Case Study of the Gaza Aquifer. *J Hydrol Eng* 2020;25(7).
3. Palestine Water Authority. Wastewater treatment plants assessment report, feasibility study for the wastewater reuse at southern part of Gaza strip. 2015. Available from: <https://www.pwa.ps/english.aspx>.
4. Hamarsheh, O., Amro, A. Epidemiology of parasitic infections in the West Bank and Gaza Strip, Palestine. *Am J Trop Med Hy.* 2020;102(2):313.
5. WHO. Drinking-water, Fact sheets. 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/drinking-water>.
6. Iticescu, C., Georgescu, L.P., Murariu, G., Circiumaru, A., Timofti, M. The characteristics of sewage sludge used on agricultural lands. AIP conference proceedings. AIP Publishing LLC; 2018. p. 20001. Available from: <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/acp/article/2022/1/020001/750811/The-characteristics-of-sewage-sludge-used-on>.
7. Gruchlik, Y., Linge, K., Joll, C. Removal of organic micropollutants in waste stabilisation ponds: A review. *J Environ Manage* 2018;206:202–14.
8. Eassa, S., Flefel, W., El-Masry, S., Abdul-Fattah, A. Evaluation of Different Diagnostic Approaches for Detection of *Cryptosporidium* in Stools of Diarrheic Children. *J High Inst Public Heal* 2017;47(1):29–38.
9. El Kelesh, E.A., Abdel-Maogood, S.Z., Abdel-Wahab, A.M. Comparative studies on some *Cryptosporidium* species infecting different animals. *Egypt Vet Med Soc Parasitol J* 2009;5:19–36.
10. Feltus, D.C., Giddings, C.W., Schneck, B.L., Monson, T., Warshauer, D., McEvoy, J.M. Evidence supporting zoonotic transmission of *Cryptosporidium* spp. in Wisconsin. *J Clin Microbiol* 2006;44(12):4303–8.
11. Nagano, S., Matsubayashi, M., Kita, T., Narushima, T., Kimata, I., Iseki, M., et al. Detection of a mixed infection of a novel *Cryptosporidium andersoni* and its subgenotype in Japanese cattle. *Vet Parasitol* 2007;149(3–4):213–8.
12. Platt, A.R., Woodhall, R.W., George, A.L. Improved DNA sequencing quality and efficiency using an optimized fast cycle sequencing protocol. *Biotechniques* 2007;43(1):58–62.
13. Khalil, I.A., Troeger, C., Rao, P.C., Blacker, B.F., Brown, A., Brewer, T.G., et al. Morbidity, mortality, and long-term consequences associated with diarrhoea from *Cryptosporidium* infection in children younger than 5 years: a meta-analysis study. *Lancet Glob Heal* 2018;6(7):e758–68.
14. Fan, Y., Wang, X., Yang, R., Zhao, W., Li, N., Guo, Y., et al. Molecular characterization of the waterborne pathogens *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia duodenalis*, *Enterocytozoon bienersi*, *Cyclospora cayentanensis* and *Eimeria* spp. in wastewater and sewage in Guangzhou, China. *Parasit Vectors* 2021;14:1–10.
15. Al-Hindi, A.I., Ghuneim, R.A., Menotti, J. Assessment of Parasitological Water Quality from House Kitchens and Desalination Plants Filters in Gaza Strip. *IUG J Nat Stud* 2021;29(2):39-52.
16. Martins, F.D.C., Ladeia, W.A., Toledo, R. dos S., Garcia, J.L., Navarro, I.T., Freire, R.L. Surveillance of *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium* in sewage from an urban area in Brazil. *Rev Bras Parasitol Veterinária* 2019;28:291–7.
17. Zahedi, A., Gofton, A.W., Greay, T., Monis, P., Oskam, C., Ball, A., et al. Profiling the diversity of *Cryptosporidium* species and genotypes in wastewater treatment plants in Australia using next generation sequencing. *Sci Total Environ* 2018;644:635–48.
18. Imre, K., Morar, A., Ilie, M.S., Plutzer, J., Imre, M., Emil, T., et al. Survey of the occurrence and human infective potential of *Giardia duodenalis* and *Cryptosporidium* spp. in wastewater and different surface water sources of western Romania. *Vector-Borne Zoonotic Dis* 2017;17(10):685–91.

19. Dyab, A.K., Monib, M.E.M., Amin, M.M., Hawary, B., Desoky, R.M. Cryptosporidiosis in immunocompromised children. *Egypt J Med Microbiol* 2018;27(2):143–9.
20. EL-Hady, H.A., Ahemd, N.S., Taha, M.A.A., Abd El-Kareem, N.M., Bakheet, R.A. Intestinal parasites in children receiving chemotherapy. *J Egypt Soc Parasitol* 2017;47(2):375–80.
21. Sabbahi, S., Ben Ayed, L., Berndtsson, R., Karanis, P. Parasitological Assessment of Sewage Sludge Samples for Potential Agricultural Reuse in Tunisia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2022;19(3):1657.
22. Yashas, S.R., Udayashankara, T.H. A Mini Review on Prevalence of Protozoan Cysts in Sewage Sludge. *Int J Eng Sci Invent* 2017;6(10):55–60.
23. Domenech, E., Amorós, I., Moreno, Y., Alonso, J.L. Cryptosporidium and Giardia safety margin increase in leafy green vegetables irrigated with treated wastewater. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2018;221(1):112–9.
24. Santos, P.R. dos, Daniel, L.A. Occurrence and removal of Giardia spp. cysts and Cryptosporidium spp. oocysts from a municipal wastewater treatment plant in Brazil. *Environ Technol* 2017;38(10):1245–54.
25. Rizk, N., Herrawy, A., Gad, M., Shaheen, M., Elmahdy, E. Existence and Removal of Rotaviruses Group A and Cryptosporidium Species in a Wastewater Treatment Plant. *Polish J Environ Stud* 2019;28(6):4331–9.
26. Sroka, J., Stojceki, K., Zdybel, J., Karamon, J., Cencek, T., Dutkiewicz, J. Occurrence of Cryptosporidium oocysts and Giardia cysts in effluent from sewage treatment plant from eastern Poland. *Ann Agric Env Med* 2013;1:57–62.
27. Bilung, L.M., Tahar, A.S., Yunos, N.E., Apun, K., Lim, YA-L., Nillian, E., et al. Detection of Cryptosporidium and Cyclospora Oocysts from Environmental Water for Drinking and Recreational Activities in Sarawak, Malaysia. *Biomed Res Int* 2017;2017:4636420.
28. Ehsan, A., Casaert, S., Levecke, B., Van Rooy, L., Pelicaen, J., Smis, A., et al. Cryptosporidium and Giardia in recreational water in Belgium. *J Water Health* 2015;13(3):870–8.
29. Ulloa-Stanojlović, F.M., Aguiar, B., Jara, L.M., Sato, M.I.Z., Guerrero, J.A., Hachich, E., et al. Occurrence of Giardia intestinalis and Cryptosporidium sp. in wastewater samples from São Paulo State, Brazil, and Lima, Peru. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 2016;23:22197–205.
30. Gallas-Lindemann, C., Sotiriadou, I., Plutzer, J., Karanis, P. Prevalence and distribution of Cryptosporidium and Giardia in wastewater and the surface, drinking and ground waters in the Lower Rhine, Germany. *Epidemiol Infect* 2013;141(1):9–21.
31. Moreno, Y., Moreno-Mesonero, L., Amorós, I., Pérez, R., Morillo, J.A., Alonso, J.L. Multiple identification of most important waterborne protozoa in surface water used for irrigation purposes by 18S rRNA amplicon-based metagenomics. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2018;221(1):102–11.
32. Ma, L., Zhang, X., Jian, Y., Li, X., Wang, G., Hu, Y., et al. Detection of Cryptosporidium and Giardia in the slaughterhouse, sewage and river waters of the Qinghai Tibetan plateau area (QTPA), China. *Parasitol Res* 2019;118:2041–51.
33. Shams, S., Abdul, Z., Khan, W., Campus, U.C.S.S. Differential techniques used for detection of cryptosporidium oocysts in stool specimens. *J Parasit Dis* 2016;1:1–11.
34. Ahmed, S.A., Karanis, P. Comparison of current methods used to detect Cryptosporidium oocysts in stools. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2018;221(5):743–63.
35. Razakandrainibe, R., Mérat, C., Kapel, N., Sautour, M., Guyot, K., Gargala, G., et al. Multicenter Evaluation of an ELISA for the Detection of Cryptosporidium spp. Antigen in Clinical Human Stool Samples. *Microorganisms* 2021;9(2):209.